

Analysis of pollutant dispersion of a DHEP and LARW aircraft design using high-fidelity simulations

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1 Abstract

The increase in air traffic and its environmental impact necessitates an assessment of the potential health risks posed by aircraft pollutants to the civil population residing near airports. Wingtip vortices, one of the most prominent wake structures, play a crucial role in the dispersion of pollutants generated by aircraft. These vortices can persist for several minutes and travel hundreds of meters before decaying. Simultaneously, the growing need to reduce pollutant emissions and noise has driven the exploration of innovative technologies such as Distributed Hybrid Electric Propulsion (DHEP) systems and Large Aspect Ratio Wings (LARW). Within this context, the European INDIGO project—a consortium of ten research and scientific institutions—aims to investigate the application of these technologies in mid-range aircraft operations and assess their impact on airport vicinities.

The complexity of pollutant dispersion, combined with the limited available data—particularly when applying DHEP and LARW technologies—necessitates the use of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) as a fundamental tool. However, accurately modeling vortical structures presents significant challenges due to the high computational demands. These arise from the large domain sizes required to predict wakes and the broad range of spatial and temporal scales necessary to capture the various phases of vortex decay. Furthermore, the method used to generate these vortices is a critical component of the modeling strategy, as it can influence subsequent wake dynamics and ultimately affect the accuracy of pollutant dispersion predictions in the near field of the aircraft. Among the available methods in the literature, the vortex sheet method—where the reactions of lift and drag forces on the air are imposed—stands out for its accuracy and its ability to model all stages of vortex evolution, including the vortex roll-up process.

The objective of this study is twofold: first, to validate the simulation results of vortex evolution using a reference aircraft configuration for which numerical data is available, and second, to extend this methodology to analyze pollutant dispersion for the initial INDIGO aircraft design (without propellers) -incorporating LARW design-, using the vortex method. The aerodynamic simulations are performed within the framework of large-eddy simulations considering real force distributions and transporting a generic scalar as a surrogate of chemical pollutant.

2 Introduction

The increasing concerns about aviation emissions' impact on health and climate, coupled with growing air traffic demand, have accelerated research into sustainable solutions. Key targets include reducing emissions of CO₂, NO_x, and soot through innovations in propulsion, aerodynamics, lightweight structures, and systems technology. Among these, Distributed Hybrid Electric Propulsion (DHEP) systems

Figure 1: Configuration of INDIGO Aircraft (left) and idealised aircraft architecture considered in current simulations (right).

and Large Aspect Ratio Wings (LARW) are particularly promising. The European INDIGO project [6] focuses on these technologies to enhance efficiency and reduce emissions and noise, especially near airports. However, the significant structural changes introduced by these designs may alter pollutant dispersion patterns, which is the primary focus of this study.

Wingtip vortices, key turbulent structures in an aircraft’s wake, are formed by the lift-induced pressure differential between the upper and lower wing surfaces. These vortices, persistent and long-lasting, significantly influence pollutant dispersion from the engines [11]. Modeling pollutant dispersion in real-world conditions, such as airports, is computationally intensive due to the need to simulate large domains and capture vortex behavior across diverse spatial and temporal scales. To circumvent the complexities of modeling full aircraft geometries and boundary layers, alternative approaches focus directly on wake vortices.

The vortex sheet method, which models lift and drag effects, effectively captures secondary vortical structures during the initial roll-up phase, a critical determinant of far-field vortex behavior [10]. These secondary structures draw energy from the primary vortices and eventually cause their decay in the far field [4]. Accurate modeling of these structures depends on mesh resolution, as demonstrated in simulations.

Previous studies validated the vortex sheet approach for commercial aircraft assuming idealized lift distributions [10, 11]. While actual distributions deviate under high-lift configurations, such as during landing, satisfactory accuracy has been demonstrated. Extensions of this method incorporate effects like sweepback angles and sideslip [15]. Additionally, [3] achieved strong agreement with high-fidelity simulations by using spanwise lift distributions as source terms in the Navier-Stokes framework, even in complex configurations involving flaps and slats.

For the INDIGO project, the selected aircraft configuration (Fig. 1, left) will undergo optimization. Current simulations focus on a simplified model excluding propellers (Fig. 1, right), resembling the Boeing Transonic Truss-Braced Wing (TTBW). This study systematically analyzes the vortex sheet method with idealized and actual force distributions, followed by an application to pollutant dispersion, culminating in conclusions.

3 Numerical framework

3.1 Governing equations and discretization

The simulations were carried out using the multi-physics Finite Element in-house code of BSC - Alya [1]. Continuity, Navier-Stokes and the species mass fractions transport equations (eqs. 1, 2 and 3, respectively) were solved for incompressible flow in the frame of Large Eddy Simulations (LES):

$$\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{u}} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{u}}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{u}}^T \otimes \bar{\mathbf{u}}) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla \bar{p}^* + (\nu + \nu_t) \Delta \bar{\mathbf{u}} + \frac{1}{\rho} \bar{\mathbf{F}}, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\phi}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{u}} \bar{\phi}) = \left(\frac{\nu}{Sc} + \frac{\nu_t}{Sc_t} \right) \Delta \bar{\phi}, \quad (3)$$

where ρ , $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$, and $\bar{\phi}$ are the density, filtered velocity, and a filtered passive scalar, respectively (Reynolds filtering is denoted with $\bar{\cdot}$). Also, ν and Sc denote the (laminar) kinematic viscosity and Schmidt number while ν_t and Sc_t their sub-grid counterparts respectively. These last contributions come from modelling the sub-grid scales (sub-grid stress tensor and sub-grid flux in eqs. 2 and 3 respectively) using the Boussinesq hypothesis where the eddy viscosity is computed from Vreman's model [14]. In addition, \bar{p}^* is a modified pressure which accounts for the pressure and the sub-grid kinetic energy (k_{sgs}), the spherical component of the sub-grid stress tensor, $\bar{p}^* = \bar{p} + 2/3k_{sgs}$.

Finally, $\bar{\mathbf{F}}$ denotes a volumetric force that is applied during the first few time steps of the simulation that mimics the reaction of lift on the air and generates the vortex roll-up. Following the methodology described in [10], a force whose magnitude remains constant along axial (x) direction but varies along the spanwise direction (y) is applied in a thin layer. Being $y = 0$ aligned with the aircraft symmetry plane, the force is expressed in the following form:

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}} = -|\bar{F}_z|\mathbf{k} = \begin{cases} -f(y)\mathbf{k}, & -B/2 \leq y \leq B/2, z_0 \leq z \leq z_0 + h, 0 \leq t \leq \tau \\ \mathbf{0}, & \text{everywhere else} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where H denotes the Heaviside step function, h is the thickness of the layer, B is the wing span, and, τ is the time during which the force is applied which was set to 0.1 s in the current simulations. It was verified through tests that the duration of force application does not significantly affect the formation and evolution of the vortices, provided that the impulse is conserved and the duration is short enough to avoid the force from persisting beyond the initial vortex generation. Similarly, no sensitivity was found to the vortex sheet thickness as long as it is greater than the cell thickness. The profile is normalised in such a way that the integral of the force along an axial distance equal to the wing chord equals the aircraft lift.

Regarding the numerical schemes, eqs. 1, 2 and 3 are discretized by applying Finite Element Method (FEM) with linear elements and solved using the in-house code Alya developed at BSC [1]. To solve Navier-Stokes equations, a second-order implicit time marching scheme [5] was used. For the scalars, an explicit Runge-Kutta of third order was utilized. The size of the time-step was set equal to 0.5 ms during the application of the force to accurately solve the first stages of the vortex roll-up and ensure stability after a high magnitude force was applied in a thin sheet. The total simulation was carried out for a physical time of 250 seconds. Once the force was removed, the timesteps were chosen based on the velocity CFL number using a factor of 2.5.

3.2 Initial conditions

To recreate the effect of atmospheric turbulence in the cases simulated in the following sections, a turbulence generator based on the works by Saad et al. [12] using a modified Von-Karman spectrum [2], similar to that used in Lin et al. [11], was adapted. Fig. 2 shows the input spectrum for the low turbulence case as well as the calculated spectrum from the initial velocity field imposed in the form of Homogeneous Isotropic Turbulence (HIT) in the domain using the turbulence generator described above.

4 Validation Using Ideal Lift Distribution

4.1 Application of Vortex Sheet

An Airbus A340 aircraft configuration is considered for the first validation case, with a wingspan length (B) of 60.3 m, lift coefficient ($C_L =$) 1.4, aspect ratio ($AR =$) 9.5, and approach speed ($V_A =$) 75m/s. In this case, an elliptical profile was considered to model the lift distribution reaction on air:

$$|\bar{F}_z| = f(y) = \frac{\rho\Gamma_0}{h\tau} \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{2y}{B}\right)^2}, \quad -B/2 \leq y \leq B/2, z_0 \leq z \leq z_0 + h, 0 \leq t \leq \tau, \quad (5)$$

Figure 2: Comparison of input and calculated spectrum

where Γ_0 is the initial maximum circulation (note: density is considered constant and uniform, therefore, the density ρ is equal to the far field density). In this case, Γ_0 is estimated to be $424 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. The initial vorticity is created according to the gradient of the following profile:

$$\frac{D\bar{\omega}_x}{Dt} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{F}_z}{\partial y} = \begin{cases} -\frac{f'(y)}{\rho} & -B/2 \leq y \leq B/2, z_0 \leq z \leq z_0 + h, 0 \leq t \leq \tau \\ 0, & \text{everywhere else} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Two counter-rotating vortices are formed at the wing-tips which rapidly roll towards each other to a mutual separation of $b_0 = 47.4\text{m}$, in agreement with results from the elliptical wing theory $b_0^{\text{theoretical}} = \pi B/4$ for the elliptical lift profile. Using theoretical formulations, the initial descent velocity comes out to be $w_0 = \frac{\Gamma_0}{2\pi b_0} = 1.42 \text{ m/s}$ and $t_0 = \frac{b_0}{w_0} = 33.33 \text{ s}$. Also, the reaction of drag on air is applied by setting the drag (D) and lift (L) distributions proportional. In this case, it is estimated that $L/D = 12$ for the given aircraft configuration and, therefore,

$$|\bar{F}_x| = \frac{L}{D} |\bar{F}_z| = \frac{L}{D} f(y), \quad -B/2 \leq y \leq B/2, z_0 \leq z \leq z_0 + h, 0 \leq t \leq \tau \quad (7)$$

The force is applied in a thin sheet of thickness (h) of around 0.5 m for a time period (τ) of 0.1s .

4.2 Domain Setup

Two meshes are considered in the following in order to understand the effect of the mesh resolution

A rectangular computational domain with dimensions $L_x \times L_y \times L_z = 8b_0 \times 5b_0 \times 5b_0$ having a structured uniform mesh with the no. of grid-points - $n_x \times n_y \times n_z = 481 \times 321 \times 351$ is used. Periodic boundary conditions are applied to opposing faces of the domain.

The initial turbulence in the atmosphere is mimicked using homogeneous isotropic turbulence (HIT), which is obtained following the methodology defined in 3.2, considering an integral length scale of 25 m and a turbulent kinetic dissipation rate (ε) of $10^{-4} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^3$ in the whole domain. A volumetric forcing term, described in 3.1 and 4.1, is applied along the vertical and axial direction in the symmetry plane of the computational domain. The influence of mesh resolution on the results is assessed in this study by the use of a finer mesh refined in y and z directions, with no. of grid-points = $n_x \times n_y \times n_z = 481 \times 481 \times 526$.

4.3 Results

For validation purposes, Fig. 3 compares the results for the two meshes considered in this work, numerical results from Lin et al. [10] and, the experiments from [9]. In the following, representations are shown using normalized time ($t^* = t/t_0$) and normalized distances ($z^* = z/b_0$ and $b^* = b/b_0$). Fig. 3 (left) shows a comparison of descent of vortex in normalized units. In the absence of dissipation, the vortex descent, caused by the velocity field induced by the other vortex should be uniform. As will be explained later, vortex circulation is dissipated in different phases (see Fig. 3 (right)), resulting

Figure 3: Temporal vortex descent (left), vortex separation (center) and comparison averaged circulation in the annulus $5 < r < 15$ m (right).

in a deceleration of the vortices in their vertical movement. Both meshes provide a very similar rate of descent with a minutely smaller velocity in the case of the coarse mesh. On the contrary, the results from the literature, where Adaptive Mesh Refinement (AMR) is used, show that the rate of vortex descent is slightly lower. Nevertheless, it is considered that these differences are minimal, and all results exhibit comparable behavior. Likewise, the separation between vortices is shown in Fig. 3 (center). A slight underprediction of the separation for the current simulations compared to that of the literature is observed, implying marginal higher velocities if the circulation is the same.

Finally, the comparison showing the circulation of the vortex averaged between radius 5-15m Γ_{5-15} , that is, $\Gamma_{r_1-r_2} = (\int_{r_1}^{r_2} \Gamma(r) dr) / (r_2 - r_1)$ with $r_1 = 5$ m and $r_2 = 15$ m, is shown in Fig. 3 (right) for completeness. The circulation is normalised with the initial averaged circulation in the described annulus $\Gamma_{5-15,0}$. It is clear that both the coarse and fine mesh cases in the present study exhibit some agreement with the experimental data, with the fine mesh demonstrating excellent correlation with the experimental results up to $t^* = 4.5$. Two distinct phases can be identified, starting with a slow diffusive-like decay phase followed by a more rapid decay. These phases are characterized by two different slopes, with the transition occurring around $t^* = 3.5$. The results show the coarse mesh is not able to recover this transition and a uniform rate of decay of circulation is obtained. In particular, the decay during the first phase is faster than that of the fine mesh while it becomes slower after the phase transition. Indeed, the coarse mesh shows one single phase during the whole evolution (for $t^* > 6$ the vortex breaks down) corresponding to the diffusion phase. The decay of circulation during the diffusion phase is attributed to the effect of the secondary vortices dissipating energy from the primary ones while during the rapid decay phase is related to the collapse of the vortex core [4]. As a consequence, the coarsening of the mesh leads to temporal reduction of circulation as a consequence of the numerical dissipation induced by the relatively large cell sizes that prevents the formation of the second phase. It can thus be concluded that discrepancies between circulation and vortex separation explain the reduced differences in descent velocity. The initial circulation was also analyzed. The initial circulation at radius b_0 (Γ_{b_0}) using both meshes was around $420 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, which is close to the theoretical initial value of $424 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. Furthermore, the initial averaged circulation between 5-15m is between $345 - 350 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, which is in good agreement with those obtained in literature ($\Gamma_{5-15} = 350$) [10].

The vortex roll-up process from the vortex sheet (fine mesh) up to a time $t^* = 0.3$ (rolling phase) is shown in Fig. 4. To show the effect of the mesh, vorticity is also shown for the coarse mesh at $t^* = 0.3$. Vortical structures are detected after the application of the λ_2 criterion [7] with a value of $\lambda_2 = -1$. Additionally, the iso-surface is colored based on the normalized tangential vorticity, which is induced by the drag force. This tangential vorticity plays a crucial role in the decay of circulation during the diffusion phase and in the evolution of the far field. [10]. Results show a qualitative similarity with those from literature [10]. Apart from the main vortices, secondary vortical structures naturally emerge due to the gradients in axial velocity originating from the drag force. Later on in the evolution phase, only the secondary vortices (rib-like structures) surrounding the primary ones survive. Such rib-like structures are attributed to play a role in the far-field decay of the vortex [10]. From the figures, it can also be observed that the coarse mesh produces fewer secondary structures because it is not able to resolve the fine scale structures responsible for the secondary vortices.

To complete the analysis, Fig. 5 shows a comparison of the evolution of vortices at different time instances for the two mesh sizes. During the evolution, it is observed that, on one hand, the secondary

structures remaining after the roll-up phase tend to dissipate, while on the other hand, instabilities in the counter-rotating vortices start growing. These instabilities can either be short-wavelength (elliptical) or long-wavelength (Crow’s instability), with a period equal to the axial domain length. It is evident that due to numerical dissipation, the secondary vortices in the coarse grid start vanishing much faster than in the fine grid case, in agreement with the reduction of the circulation caused by the effect of the secondary vortices. For this mesh, it is observed how the primary vortices are broken down by the end of the evolution shown in Figs. 5. The same pattern would be observed for the fine mesh when simulated for a longer time.

Hence, the results demonstrate the vortex sheet methodology can reproduce vortices with an acceptable level of accuracy and will be used to describe the dispersion of pollutants by the aircraft wake. Also it has been shown that the method features a sensitivity to the mesh resolution which is manifested in a loss of structures and a faster vortex decay.

Figure 4: Isosurface of $\lambda_2 = -0.3$ with coloured contours of $\omega_\theta^* = \omega_\theta t_0$ (normalized tangential vorticity) during roll-up phase.

5 Exact Lift Distribution Case

Since exact lift distribution data of most of commercial aircraft are not readily available, for convenience elliptical distribution is typically assumed. However, replacing the elliptical force distribution in the sheet with the actual force distribution along the span can further improve the accuracy of this method in predicting the characteristics of the vortices and their evolution. The application of force as a source term in the Navier-Stokes equations is given by

$$|\bar{F}_z| = \frac{\rho \Gamma_0}{h \tau} g(y), \quad (8)$$

where $g(y)$ is an even function in y , whose value is 1 at $y = 0$. The use of body force to simulate a wing with complex (and exact) configuration has been done by [3], which motivated the use of the exact lift distribution in the vortex sheet method.

5.1 Case Set-Up

In an ideal scenario without computational constraints, the approach would involve simulating the complete aircraft geometry (LARW) and modeling pollutant dispersion within its wake under various operating conditions. However, given the aforementioned constraints, a more practical alternative is to model pollutant dispersion based on the vortices generated using the previously described methodology. This approach simplifies the problem by reducing the aerodynamic effects of the entire aircraft to a body force, significantly lowering computational costs. Additionally, it is necessary to validate this force-based method for the INDIGO aircraft. This aspect will be addressed in this section.

Figure 5: Isosurface of $\lambda_2 = -1$ with coloured contours of $\omega_\theta^* = \omega_\theta t_0$ (normalized tangential vorticity). Results for coarse mesh (left column) and fine mesh (right column).

The flow structure of the wake generated by the wing is compared by running simulations in Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) and LES framework. First, an external aerodynamic simulation of the wing-strut configuration of INDIGO Aircraft was run using the RANS methodology. After obtaining the lift distribution from this simulation, LES was run using lift distribution as body force and the wake generated using two methodologies are compared. This wing corresponds to an initial configuration from the INDIGO project which is supported by a strut to allow a larger span.

RANS: a model of INDIGO Aircraft wing along with the strut (see Fig. 6) is simulated using RANS with Spallart Allmaras model in SU2 software [13] using mesh adaptation based on vorticity. Since the wing-strut assembly is symmetric, only one-half of the geometry is simulated in the hemispherical domain to save computational resources. The hemispherical domain of radius 450 m with around 22 million cells (unstructured) is chosen to simulate airflow over the wing-strut configuration (span = 51.439 m) with a free stream velocity of around 84.6 m/s. Only wing-strut configuration is considered for the validation part because the wing tip vortices and the vortices originating from struts are much more dominant when compared to other parts of the aircraft wake and have a longer lifetime than other wake structures [11]. Moreover, this also saved computational resources that would have been consumed in modelling fuselage.

LES: a rectangular domain of size $L_x \times L_y \times L_z = 379.2 \times 237 \times 237 \text{ m}^3$ with no. of grid-points

$n_x \times n_y \times n_z = 481 \times 321 \times 351$ is considered. The case configuration, initialization, and boundary conditions used for this case were the same as the LES simulation for the vortex sheet method described in section 4. In this case, the combined lift and drag distributions generated by the wing and strut along the span of the wing, computed from RANS simulation, were applied in a thin sheet with a width of the span of the wing. Therefore, compared to the validation (in earlier sections), the main difference is the application of realistic force distributions for a complex wing configuration. The complete structure of the wing was divided in narrow fringes along the wing chord in order to obtain the force distribution. The pressure differences between the two surfaces of the wing and the strut, calculated from the RANS, were added for each of these slices and divided by the fringe width (in the spanwise direction).

5.2 Results and Findings

The function $g(y)$ obtained from lift distribution using actual combined (wing-strut) configuration is shown in Fig. 6. This curve is quite different from the ellipse and thus shows that actual lift distribution can strongly differ from an elliptical distribution. The drag distribution is assigned as the product of lift and $\frac{L}{D}$ for a high lift configuration[8]. Integrating eq. (8) and equating to the lift force it is obtained that the maximum initial circulation is around $127 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. The validation work was only carried out for the near field due to the constraint on the computational capability of RANS simulation and the extremely large domains that the simulation of the far field would require (recall that the RANS domain is spherical). Hence, the comparison between RANS and LES is limited to the nascent vortex with the vortex sheet. For the RANS simulation, the vortex in a plane (perpendicular to freestream velocity direction) at a distance 4 m from the wing is considered while for the LES simulation, the median plane containing the vortex is chosen at $t = 0.1$ s (after the body force disappears). Both scenarios depict the initial phase of vortex formation, characterized by the presence of a vortex sheet, which occurs when the wing moves away, leaving behind a vortex sheet and a nascent vortex. Since this section of the results is produced using very different methodologies, circulation was the best criterion for comparing both vortices in the near field. The circulation at different radii of the vortex is compared in Table 1, where the first column shows the radius (in m) and the second and third columns show the circulation (in m^2/s) for the LES and RANS results, respectively.

Table 1: Comparison of Circulation Values

Radius (in m)	Circulation (Vortex Sheet) (in m^2/s)	Circulation (RANS-Wing Modelling) (in m^2/s)
25	128.20	129.51
20	119.35	119.12
18	112.79	112.578
15	98.61	101.29
8	70.25	72.80
5	55.73	56.61

From the table, it is evident that the circulation profiles of the vortices in the two cases are very close to each other. Qualitatively as well, the plots of vorticity from the two simulations are similar to each other as shown in Fig. 7. The main difference between them is the higher thickness of the vortex sheet in LES simulation (recall that the simulation results are independent of the initial thickness of the sheet as long as thickness ll wingspan) and higher value of peak vorticity at vortex center in RANS case (vortex center is indeed a singularity and peak vorticity at center increases with refinement) owing to finer mesh in RANS by using adaptive mesh refinement in higher vorticity region. These aspects are related to the mesh resolution and are not considered to affect the subsequent flow evolution as shown in Table 1, where the vorticity field integrated over the circulation for both simulations are in good agreement. Moreover, the separation between the core of the vortices was also very close, being 50.36 and 50.88 m for the LES and RANS, respectively.

The results validate the assumption that the near-field wake generated using the vortex sheet method with an exact lift distribution has good level of accuracy. The effectiveness of this method has already

been demonstrated for far-field analysis in section 4. Therefore, this approach, incorporating the exact lift distribution, can be reliably utilized for studying pollutant dispersion by the INDIGO aircraft.

Figure 6: Wing configuration (left) and associated normalized lift force computed from RANS simulations.

Figure 7: Nascent Vortex from RANS (left) and vortex sheet from LES (right) comparison.

6 Dispersion of Pollutants

Once the capabilities of the vortex sheet model to reproduce the flow evolution have been validated, the dispersion of pollutants issuing from the engine and their subsequent evolution under the effect of the counter-rotating vortices is analysed for both the elliptical force profile corresponding to a standard wing and the realistic distribution from the INDIGO aircraft. The dispersion of pollutants in this case is represented by a passive scalar that represents the mixing between the engine exhaust composition with the ambient air since the plume is considered in this initial approximation as non-reactive and with constant density. Therefore, a passive scalar transport equation, see eq. 3, is solved along with the continuity and momentum equations in the context of LES using a 3rd order Runge Kutta explicit scheme for time integration.

6.1 Case set-up

1. Conventional Aircraft Case: the case configuration, initialization, and boundary conditions correspond to those explained in section 4. The rectangular domain is discretized using a structured uniform mesh with no. of grid points = $n_x \times n_y \times n_z = 481 \times 481 \times 526$. Exhaust plumes emerging from 4 engines of Airbus A340 were considered. The plume is represented by a volumetric cylindrical field oriented along the axial direction, which interacts with the vortices generated by the wake using the vortex sheet method. The diameter of each plume (1.33 m) was set to twice

Figure 8: Isosurface of scalar concentrations representing the plumes for the conventional aircraft case at $t=0.1$ s (left) and 10 s (right).

the diameter of the aircraft engine exhaust exit. The passive scalar value within the plume is 0.25, derived from an initial magnitude of 1 at the engine exhaust, which then diluted to 0.25 as it spread within the plume. The total physical time for which this simulation is ran is 250 s.

2. INDIGO Aircraft Case: in this case, the effects of the pollutant dispersion from the INDIGO Aircraft were compared by making it equivalent to the Airbus A340 aircraft considered in the previous section in terms of weight/lift generation. The lift and span of the INDIGO aircraft were hence scaled accordingly without changing the design or configuration of the aircraft/lift-producing device. The scaled span is 106.34 m (B) and the lift generated by the new configuration is 1.84×10^6 N (weight of Airbus A340). The initial separation of the vortices (b_0) is assumed to be 83.5 m (using elliptical wing theory). Although the initial separation obtained through the distribution is expected to be smaller than the case of ideal elliptical distribution (from results in subsection 5.2), a larger value of 83.5 is used. The domain size based on that is $L_x \times L_y \times L_z = 8b_0 \times 5b_0 \times 5b_0$ with no. of grid-points = $n_x \times n_y \times n_z = 481 \times 481 \times 526$. This configuration is similar to the fine mesh settings in section 4 which gave satisfactory results. The low turbulence setting used in 4 for the initial condition for generating HIT. As a final note, to add that the normalization of quantities like time, distance, and concentration in the present case has been done by values used in the conventional aircraft case to facilitate a direct comparison between the two cases.

6.1.1 Results

The four plumes left behind the engines of the Airbus A340 are shown in Fig. 8 using isosurfaces of the scalar concentration at two different time instants corresponding to early and fully developed flow conditions $t = 0.1, 10$ s. It is observed that after 10 s, the four plumes have collapsed into the two vortices created by the lift force. The high concentrations of scalars appear to accumulate around the vortex core and continue to move with it throughout the evolution phase. The existence of this phenomenon can be clearly distinguished in Fig. 9, which shows the descent of the vortex core, similar to Fig. 3, and the position of the maximum concentration of the scalar along with it, which can be used to quantify the level of dissipation of the pollutant concentration by the wing-tip vortices, for the two architectures. These results demonstrate that the dispersion of pollutants is not influenced by the shape or size of the plume, but it is entirely governed by the dynamics of the vortex.

During the temporal evolution of pollutants, two major phases are detected: for the conventional aircraft, the first phase is between $t^* = 0$ and $t^* = 0.3$ (Fig. 9 (right)) where the maximum value dips from 1 to 0.056 in 10 s. This is due to the strong turbulent mixing of the pollutants during the vortex roll-up phase. After the roll-up is completed at around 10 s ($t^* = 0.3$) the pollutant concentrations are already sucked into the core and the rate of change in value throughout the remaining time is less drastic. However, there is still a steep drop (compared to later phases) in concentration till $t^* = 1$; after which the rate of decrease is slightly reduced until $t^* = 4.5$. In the last phase of evolution, the decrease in the value of scalar maxima is again more rapid due to the rapid decay and dissociation of the vortex after the rapid decay phase is initiated. At this point, the core is dissociated into many small chunks which further dilute the concentration. Therefore, Fig. 9 (right) illustrates how vortex dynamics govern

Figure 9: Comparison of Descent of Passive maxima (left), evolution of maximum concentration value with zoom in the low ordinates range (center) and complete evolution of the maximum concentration value for the conventional aircraft (right).

the dilution of pollutants for an elliptical force profile. Specifically, during the roll-up phase, the rate of dilution is at its peak, followed by the onset of the rapid decay phase. Consequently, accurate modeling of vortex dynamics is crucial for reliable pollutant dispersion predictions.

On the contrary, the evolution is qualitatively different in the case of the INDIGO aircraft. The results for this case show high concentrations of the pollutant concentrations trapped around the core of the vortex. Despite the vortices, in this case, are weaker as compared to those of the conventional aircraft (owing to LARW) configuration ($230\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ against $424\text{m}^2/\text{s}$), the vortex is still strong enough to trap high concentrations of pollutants around the core throughout the evolution phase. The same plot also shows how the vortices and the maximum concentration descend much more slowly towards the ground when compared to the conventional aircraft, owing to the low circulation of the vortex and higher separation between them. This gives more time for pollutants to disperse (under different factors like cross-winds, ambient turbulence, etc.) before they reach the ground. It can be seen that the concentration maxima for the INDIGO aircraft decreases very rapidly initially and then stagnates to a constant value for the rest of the evolution time. Based on these observations, it is expected that a lower concentration of pollutants will descend a given distance in the case of INDIGO Aircraft compared to conventional aircraft.

7 Conclusions and future work

This work aims to provide insights on how pollutant dispersion is affected due to the wing-tip vortices created by the aircraft as a consequence of lift and drag. For this purpose, the capability of vortex sheet method to produce the aerodynamic lift-derived wakes is validated thoroughly. This method has been chosen since it provides, with minimal extra load in the case set-up, an accurate description of the wake evolution, especially for conditions in which drag force may be important as happens in landing making it appropriate for the study of pollutants dispersion in the nearby airport region.

The study focused on validating the method using both coarse and fine meshes for an idealized lift profile, analyzing the initial roll-up phase and far-field evolution. Results indicated that mesh resolution significantly influences the flow dynamics due to the role of secondary vorticity generated by drag forces. The validation is further extended to compare RANS and LES results during the early stages of vortex evolution, incorporating the real force distribution caused by the complex wing structure, including a strut, as proposed in Project INDIGO. Excellent agreement is observed in the spatial distribution of circulation. Following validation, the method is applied to analyze pollutant dispersion caused by wing-tip vortices for both an idealized elliptical force profile and the real force distribution of the INDIGO aircraft.

The analysis revealed that vortices can trap high concentrations of pollutants around the core, regardless of the plume's shape or size. The study also demonstrated that, despite the vortices generated by the INDIGO aircraft being significantly weaker, they were still capable of trapping and transporting high concentrations of pollutants throughout their evolution. Furthermore, the descent rate of the INDIGO aircraft vortices is notably lower compared to conventional aircraft. Additionally, the pollutant dilution rate for the INDIGO aircraft is initially more rapid, resulting in a more diluted concentration

of pollutants at a specific height after a given time.

In future works, the effect of the temperature stratification and ground effect will be investigated on both the vortex and pollutant dynamics when accounting for realistic wing force profiles.

8 Acknowledgments

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

References

- [1] M. V. Azquez, G. Houzeaux, S. Koric, A. Artigues, J. Aguado-Sierra, R. Arís, D. Mira, H. Calmet, F. Cucchietti, H. Owen, A. Taha, E. D. Burness, J. José, M. Cela, and M. Valero. Alya: Multiphysics engineering simulation towards exascale, 2016.
- [2] W. Bechara, C. Bailly, P. Lafonj, and S. M. Candel. Stochastic approach to noise modeling for free turbulent flows, 1994.
- [3] S. Bennie and M. Fossati. Wake vortex - exhaust interactions downstream of high-lift aircraft geometries using a residual source term method. In *AIAA Aviation Forum and ASCEND, 2024*. American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics Inc, AIAA, 2024.
- [4] F. Holzäpfel, T. Hofbauer, D. Darracq, H. Moet, F. Garnier, and C. F. Gago. Analysis of wake vortex decay mechanisms in the atmosphere. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 7:263–275, 6 2003.
- [5] G. Houzeaux and J. Principe. A variational subgrid scale model for transient incompressible flows. *International Journal of Computational Fluid Dynamics*, 22(3):135–152, 2008.
- [6] INDIGO project. <https://indigo-sustainableaviation.eu/>. *website*, 2024.
- [7] J. Jeong and F. Hussain. On the identification of a vortex. *Journal of fluid mechanics*, 285:69–94, 1995.
- [8] S. Keye. Fluid-structure coupled analysis of a transport aircraft and flight-test validation. *Journal of Aircraft*, 48:381–390, 2011.
- [9] F. Köpp, S. Rahm, I. Smalikhov, A. Dolfi, J. P. Cariou, M. Harris, and R. I. Young. Comparison of wake-vortex parameters measured by pulsed and continuous-wave lidars. *Journal of Aircraft*, 42:916–923, 2005.
- [10] M. LIN, G. CUI, and Z. ZHANG. A new vortex sheet model for simulating aircraft wake vortex evolution. *Chinese Journal of Aeronautics*, 30:1315–1326, 8 2017.
- [11] M. LIN, W. HUANG, Z. ZHANG, C. XU, and G. CUI. Numerical study of aircraft wake vortex evolution near ground in stable atmospheric boundary layer. *Chinese Journal of Aeronautics*, 30:1866–1876, 12 2017.
- [12] T. Saad, D. Cline, R. Stoll, and J. C. Sutherland. Scalable tools for generating synthetic isotropic turbulence with arbitrary spectra. *AIAA Journal*, 55:327–331, 2017.
- [13] SU2 code. <https://github.com/su2code/su2>. *website*, 2024.
- [14] A. W. Vreman. An eddy-viscosity subgrid-scale model for turbulent shear flow: Algebraic theory and applications. *Physics of Fluids*, 16:3670–3681, 2004.
- [15] Z. Xu, D. Li, and J. Cai. Long-wave deformation of in-ground-effect wake vortex under crosswind condition. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 142, 11 2023.